

Dimers of Diethynyl-Conjugated Zinc-Phthalocyanine as Hole Selective Layers for Perovskites solar cells Fabrication

Meenakshi Pegu,^{a,†} Desiré Molina,^{b,†} Maria J. Álvaro-Martins,^b María Castillo,^b Lydia Ferrer,^b Peng Huang,^a Samrana Kazim,^{a,c} Ángela Sastre-Santos,^{b*} Shahzada Ahmad^{a,c*}

We developed triple bonded π -conjugated zinc-phthalocyanine dimers (**ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc-t-t-ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3**) through molecular engineering, these dimers were then employed as hole selective layers for perovskite solar cells (PSCs) fabrication. The designed dimers showed band alignment with mixed cation perovskite, and efficient charge extraction capability, thus allowing improvement in the photocurrent density and subsequently performance of the PSCs. The fabricated PSC with dimer **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3** measured a power conversion efficiency of 18.32%, which surpasses the PSC based on the state-of-the-art Spiro-OMeTAD (17.42%). **ZnPc** dimers displayed improved long-term stability under stress conditions such as moisture and thermal.

1. Introduction

Halide perovskites are being considered a new paradigm for sustainable energy harvesting owing to their potentially attractive optoelectronic properties, such as high absorption coefficients and long carrier diffusion lengths, tolerance to defects, and the possibility of processing from solutions at low temperatures.¹⁻³ Their application in photovoltaic (PV) further promises flexibility, lightweight, and efficient performances. The perovskite solar cells (PSCs) performances comparably match with mature silicon-based cells (27.6%), measuring power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) up to 25.7%.^{4,5} Nevertheless, the vital challenge for PSCs to be commercially exploited is the lack of long-term stability against moisture, heat, and prolonged light soaking results in ion migration and segregation.⁶ The charge-selective layers play a decisive role in achieving the performance of PSCs.⁷⁻⁹ In a PSCs the photoactive perovskite layer is sandwiched between the hole transporting material (HTM) and the electron transporting material (ETM).¹⁰⁻¹³ Based on the stacking of each layer, the PSCs architecture can be of mesoscopic (*n-i-p*) and inverted planar (*p-i-n*) configuration. The highest PCE (>25%) was measured in the *n-i-p* structure device while the *p-i-n* (planar) PSCs hold the merit of easy fabrication and versatility in terms of energy band engineering. The use of HTM is essential in promoting efficient charge extraction and transport, and suppression of the photoinduced carrier recombination. Arguably, the HTMs play a vital role in the stability of PSCs to isolate and protect the active layer from moisture. Various families of HTMs have been developed and they can be polymers or single molecules.¹⁰ The widely used and state-of-the-art HTMs are the single-molecule 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis(*N,N*-di-*p*-methoxyphenylamine)-9,9'-spirobifluorene (Spiro-OMeTAD) and the polymer poly-(triarylamine) (PTAA), that delivered high PCEs but are cost-uncompetitive and induce instability over time.^{14,15}

Phthalocyanines (Pc) are known to be robust semiconducting materials with remarkable optoelectronic properties, such as an intense absorption in the visible and near-infrared region, excellent thermal and chemical stability, and chemical versatility.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Such merits led to the Pcs application in multiple technologies, including photosensitizers for photodynamic therapy against cancer, as active materials in organic solar cells, in gas sensors, etc.^{20,21} Pcs have been employed as HTMs layer in PSCs^{17,22,23} and a nickel phthalocyanine based dopant-free HTM gave an efficient performance in the PSCs.²⁴ While, zinc phthalocyanines as HTM in PSCs, yielded a PCE of 17.5%.²⁵ Notably, PSCs with Pcs as HTM are usually more stable against deterioration than those of reference devices.²⁶⁻²⁸ Pc dimers are known to be used in the application of controllable molecular switches, and their large delocalization and high charge mobility favors them to be the new class of semiconductor materials.^{29,30}

Zinc-phthalocyanine (ZnPc) dimers³¹ are competitive HTMs, to balance the trade of stability and performance.³² ZnPc-DPP-ZnPc (Figure 1) resulted in the best PCE when applied as dopant-free HTM in *n-i-p* type PSCs, reaching 16.8% PCE, and also showed improved stability as compared to the Spiro-OMeTAD based devices. It is worth highlighting the planar molecular structures, that can favor the mobility of charges in the solid state.³² Rather, such structures can aggregate forming extensive crystalline domains that result in incomplete coverage as well as overly thick layers. Three-dimensional (3D) structures can solve this issue since less intense intermolecular interactions lead to more uniform layers. A well-designed 3D molecule will result in a layer of controlled thickness with adequate charge mobility. Here, the study of three diethynyl conjugated ZnPc dimers as HTMs is presented (**ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc-t-t-ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3**, Figure 1). For the ease of reading here on, we have referred to the ZnPc dimers **ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc-t-t-ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3** as **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** respectively. Diketopyrrolopyrrole (DPP) is a well-known electron-deficient building block and its potential as active material due to its higher carrier mobility and surface morphology has been documented.³³ A strong π - π stacking is induced in the solid-state due to the planar molecular core and strong supramolecular interaction is favored. Additionally, the alkyl substituents also help in fine-tuning intermolecular packing structures and therefore render tunable charge transport properties. Moreover, the larger polarizability of the sulfur atoms of the thiophene heterocycle stabilizes the molecular system and valence band of the frontier molecular orbitals and the two oxygen atoms in the fused ring enhance the molecular dipole, constructing an internal electrical field to facilitate the charge transport.²⁴ Additionally, the more polarizable sulfur atoms can induce effective mobility that is desirable to achieve higher current density. **ZnPc 1** represents a simple modification of **ZnPc-DPP-ZnPc** that involves binding the DPP to the ZnPc rings through

triple bonds to distinguish the impact of a higher degree of self-organization (π - π aggregation) for device application. The inclusion of the triple bonds along the π -linker in the ZnPc dimers allows co-planarity in the molecular core structure of the HTMs.³⁴ **ZnPc 2** is a simplify structure with two contiguous triple bonds as linkers of both ZnPc macrocycles. In this context, to obtain a 3D structure, we designed a new dimer containing 2',7'-diethynylfluorene as the linker element (**ZnPc 3**). Spirobifluorene based building blocks have been extensively investigated in organic semiconductors for organic electronics, owing to the existence of the sp^3 hybrid atoms at the junction of the π -conjugated system, the fluorene-based molecule offers advantages such as the high glass transition temperature (T_g), morphological stability and excellent solubility.

Figure 1. Structure of Pc dimers **ZnPc-DPP-ZnPc**, **ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc-t-t-ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3**.

2. Results and Discussions

The three ZnPc dimers were the products of Sonogashira couplings. Dimer **ZnPc 1** was synthesized per our previous report³³ from iodophthalocyanine **4** with diethynyl-DPP **5** with a 30% yield (Scheme 1a). To improve the yield of **ZnPc 1**, we carried out the synthesis from ethynylphthalocyanine **6** and dibrominated DPP **7** (Scheme 1b). However, using this route we obtained **ZnPc 1** in only an 8% yield due to the appearance of high homocoupling products. **ZnPc 2** was synthesized according to the literature.³⁵ **ZnPc 3** was also initially synthesized from ethynylphthalocyanine **6** and the corresponding dibromo derivative **8** in 15% yield (Scheme 1c), although the performance was improved up to 54% by coupling iodophthalocyanine **4** and diethynylspirofluorene **9** (Scheme 1d). **ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3** were fully characterized by ¹H NMR, UV-Vis, and FTIR spectrophotometry, and MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry; **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3** was characterized by ¹H NMR and MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry (Figure S1-S2).

The three dimers are readily soluble in THF, although **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3** are less soluble in common organic solvents, however, **ZnPc 2** is nearly soluble in solvents such as chloroform, chlorobenzene, and dichloromethane at room temperature.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of **ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc 1**, a) by the route previously described and b) the new route. Synthesis of **ZnPc-t-Spiro-t-ZnPc 3** c) by route 1 and d) route 2.

Spectroscopic and electrochemistry and Structural studies

The UV-Vis absorption properties of the ZnPc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** were studied in THF solution as well as in thin films form (Figure 2a, 2b, Table 1). The absorption spectra of Pcs exhibit two typical characteristic bands, which are usually the B bands located around 250-350 nm in the ultraviolet region, and the Q band that appears at a higher wavelength region around

500-750 nm. Notably, the Pcs are highly conjugated molecules, thus the absorption maxima corresponding to the Q bands appear at longer wavelengths, 709 nm, 703 nm, and 690 nm for **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**, respectively. The bathochromic shifts of the phthalocyanines can be ascribed to the intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) transitions. It can be deduced from the absorption spectra, the Q bands of the dimers appear to split into two by the existence of several regioisomers with a non-symmetric character that induces π - π^* excitation between the bonding and the antibonding molecular orbitals.³⁶ **ZnPc 1** has a lower molar extinction coefficient, probably it tends to stack more than the other dimers even in dilute solutions. The absorption spectra of the thin films display a large broadening for the Q bands which reflects the strong molecular interactions.

To investigate the potential application of **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** as HTMs in PSCs. We determined energy alignment with the help of cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements. The solution of phthalocyanines was prepared in THF and measured to deduce the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) (Figure 2c, Table 1). The redox couple ferrocene/ferricenium ion (Fc/Fc⁺) was used as the external standard, and 4.8 eV below the vacuum was noted as the reference level. HOMO values were favorable to extract holes from the active layer and similar for the three derivatives (-4.89 eV, -5.00 eV, and -4.87 eV for **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**, respectively). The hole extraction ability of the developed HTMs was noted to be worthy of device integration. According to the calculated LUMO values, while **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** (-3.16 eV, -3.67 eV, and -3.64 eV, respectively) could effectively block electrons. The energy level band diagram of **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** is in alignment with the perovskite used (Figure 2d).

Figure 2. UV-Visible spectra of Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**, (a) in THF solution, (b) in thin films, (c) cyclic voltammetry of Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** in THF solutions, and (d) energy level band diagram of ZnPc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**.

To evaluate the influence of the ZnPc dimers as HTMs on the perovskite layer, the absorption was measured (Figure 3a). We noted higher absorption intensity peaks with the Pcs as over-layer as compared to the only perovskite. Metal phthalocyanines also show light absorption properties in the near-infrared (NIR) region. The higher absorption for ZnPc dimers in the range of 550-800 nm could be assumed due to the Q-band transition and hence its addition as an HTM layer on the top of perovskite influenced the optical wavelength of the perovskite/HTM thin films in the region 550-780 nm.

Table 1. Optical and electrochemical parameters of **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2** and **ZnPc 3**.

HTM	λ_{abs} (nm) ^a	E_{red1} (eV)	E_{ox1} (eV)	$E_{\text{g, EC}}^{\text{b}}$	HOMO ^c	LUMO ^d	μ ($10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	σ ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)
ZnPc 1	670/709	-1.64	0.09	1.73	-4.89	-3.16	2.83	1.05
ZnPc 2	671/703	-1.13	0.20	1.33	-5.00	-3.67	1.5	0.51
ZnPc 3	671/690	-1.16	0.07	1.23	-4.87	-3.64	4.08	1.23

^aAbsorption spectra were measured in THF solution. ^b $E_{\text{g, EC}}$ (eV) was calculated by $E_{\text{g, EC}} = E_{\text{red1}} - E_{\text{ox1}}$. ^cHOMO (eV) was calculated by HOMO = LUMO - $E_{\text{g, EC}}$ (eV).

^dLUMO (eV) was calculated by LUMO = $-|E_{\text{red1}} \text{ (vs. Fc/Fc}^+)| + 4.8$ (CV).

We performed the steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurement for the perovskite and with ZnPc dimers as HTMs, Pcs coated perovskite shows quenching, indicating the effectiveness of HTMs in hole extraction (Figure 3b). The π - π stacking present in the Pcs with the peripheral groups allows the favorable interface with the perovskite layer that favors PL quenching. **ZnPc 3** showed the maximum PL quenching behavior, followed by **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 2**.

Lower surface roughness and uniform film coverage of an HTM play a role in enhancing PV performances in PSCs, we recorded the surface microstructure of the perovskite (Figure S3) and with Pcs under undoped conditions (Figure 4a-c). The Pcs exhibit a uniform capping layer deposition with fewer pinholes in the undoped state on perovskites. However, under a doped state (Figure S4) the

microstructure of **ZnPc 1** aggregates on the top of the perovskite layer with less uniformity, resulting in incomplete coverage and defect formation. While **ZnPc 2** and **ZnPc 3** showed a similar pattern in morphology and uniformity in the surface coverage.

Figure 3: (a) Absorbance spectra of PSK and with Pc dimers (**ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**) thin films, and (c) photoluminescence (PL) spectra of PSK and with Pc dimers (**ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**) thin films.

We measured the surface properties induced by Pcs by goniometry measurements. The contact angle value for only perovskite (Figure S5), and with undoped **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** was found to be 75°, and 96°, 93°, 95° (inset Figure 4a-c); while under the doping conditions, we noted reduced contact angle values to 78°, 79°, and 81° (Figure S6) for **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** respectively. The use of hygroscopic dopant compromises the surface properties.

Figure 4: Surface SEM images and contact angle measurements of Pc dimers. Undoped ZnPcs (a) **ZnPc 1**, (b) **ZnPc 2**, and (c) **ZnPc 3**, as HTMs on the surface of perovskite layer thin films.

Electrical properties and Device performance

We perform the space-charge-limit-current (SCLC) measurement to measure hole mobility (μ) with the device architecture FTO/PEDOT:PSS/HTM/Au. The hole mobility (Figure 5a) was calculated from the J - V curves by fitting to the Mott-Gurney law ($J = 9\epsilon\epsilon_0\mu V_{app}^2/8L^3$). The doped **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** showed hole mobilities of 2.83×10^{-5} , 1.5×10^{-5} , and $4.08 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, while doped Spiro-OMeTAD was found to be 1.19×10^{-4} . **ZnPc 3** showed better hole extracting and transporting behavior, corresponding to molecular conjugation and π - π stacking. We probed the charge transport properties of **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** by measuring the linear current vs voltage (I - V) profile (Figure 5b) of the device (FTO/HTM/Au) under dark conditions. The calculated conductivities were found to be 1.05, 0.51, and $1.23 \mu\text{Scm}^{-1}$ for **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** respectively. To evaluate the Pcs as HTMs in PSCs we fabricated n - i - p devices as FTO/bl-meso TiO_2 / $(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}$ /HTM/Au (Figure 5c). The short circuit current (J_{sc}), open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), and fill factor (FF), under simulated AM 1.5G solar illumination at 100 mW cm^{-2} , of the PSCs with Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**, and Spiro-OMeTAD as HTMs are presented (Figure 5d), and tabulated (Table 2). We noted the optimized concentration is 15 mM, for **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** as HTMs for PSCs. The Pcs were doped with tert-butyl pyridine (t -BP) and lithium bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide (Li-TFSi) as dopants. The PSC based on **ZnPc 3** as HTM demonstrated a PCE of 18.32%, (V_{oc} of 1039 mV, J_{sc} of 23.63 mAcm^{-2} , and FF of 74.62%), outperformed the performance of Spiro-OMeTAD based PSC with a PCE of 17.42% (V_{oc} 1059 mV, J_{sc} 22.84 mAcm^{-2} , FF 71.97%). The competitive performance of **ZnPc 3** is in agreement with our electro-optical characterization. **ZnPc 1** (PCE 16.49%) and **ZnPc 2** (PCE 12.82%) comparatively showed lower performance.

Figure 5: (a) Hole mobility curves, (b) conductivity measurement curves; of the devices based on Spiro-OMeTAD and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**, (c) adopted architect of ZnPcs in PSC, (d) J - V curves of the PSCs, (e) IPCE graph of PSCs with Spiro-OMeTAD and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**, (f) J - V curves of the PSCs based on undoped and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**, (g) steady-state MPPT measurement for 300s of the based on Spiro-OMeTAD and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, **ZnPc 3**, and (h) MPP tracking of the PSCs based on Spiro-OMeTAD and **ZnPc 3** under light for at 0.8 V around 1 sun illumination.

The plausible reason for the lower performance could be the lower solubility in the preferred solvent or the molecular aggregation that hinders the effective energetic coupling of the layers, resulting in lower device PCE. We ascribed the improved current density (J_{sc}) of **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3** to the effective hole extraction at the interfaces, as noted from PL spectra and higher carrier concentration. In addition, the presence of DPP as a linker in the dimer **ZnPc 1** and fluorene-mediated linker in dimer **ZnPc 3** contributes to the charge extraction and carrier mobility and enhancement in J_{sc} . The PSCs statistics with ZnPcs including V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF , and PCE are presented (Figure S7 a-d).

The incident photon-to-current conversion efficiency (IPCE) spectra of PSCs with the Spiro-OMeTAD and dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** were measured (Figure 5e). The IPCE spectra display a broad response from 300-800 nm, showing a plateau between 400-700nm with a value of >80% for Spiro-OMeTAD and with Pc dimers **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3**, however, **ZnPc 2** showed a lower IPCE response, correlating with J - V measurements.

Table 2: PSCs parameters with various HTM in pristine and doped form.

HTM	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mAcm^{-2})	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Spiro-OMeTAD	1059	22.84	71.97	17.42
ZnPc 1	1030	23.21	68.93	16.49
Avg.	1026 \pm 0.014	22.53 \pm 1.06	63.58 \pm 5.3	14.83 \pm 1.65
Undoped	1026	22.27	64.34	14.71
Avg.	1020 \pm 0.0075	21.33 \pm 0.938	62.50 \pm 7.37	13.68 \pm 1.023
ZnPc 2	1041	22.25	55.30	12.82
Avg.	1030 \pm 0.01	19.5 \pm 2.75	49.49 \pm 5.8	9.88 \pm 2.82
Undoped	1021	19.45	56.12	11.17
Avg.	1000 \pm 0.115	19.14 \pm 0.421	53.06 \pm 3.02	10.28 \pm 0.89
ZnPc 3	1039	23.63	74.62	18.32
Avg.	1020 \pm 0.012	23.18 \pm 0.44	72.46 \pm 2.44	17.41 \pm 0.91
Undoped	1014	22.49	61.47	14.03
Avg.	1010 \pm 0.016	21.74 \pm 0.738	60.83 \pm 1.13	13.45 \pm 0.571

We further fabricated n - i - p type PSCs to evaluate the performances of undoped ZnPc dimers (**ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**) and doped Spiro-OMeTAD as a control. The PV parameters for undoped ZnPc dimers are illustrated in **Table 2** and the statistical device performance is depicted (Figure S8). Arguably, doped Spiro-OMeTAD showed higher performance than the undoped ZnPc dimers

(Figure 5f), notably, the undoped ZnPc dimers with **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3** yielded a PCE of 14.71% and 14.03%, respectively; and **ZnPc 2** of 11.17%. The ZnPc dimers also showed a competitive performance in their pristine form i.e., undoped state, and by further optimization and design-principal rule, it can outperform doped Spiro-OMeTAD in PSCs. Expectedly, in the doped state, we noted an increase in the PCE values as compared to its undoped state. We hypothesized the improved PV performances of the doped HTMs could be due to the higher carrier concentration, and lowering of the valence band (VB) of the ZnPc dimers that align to the valence band of the perovskite layer and improves the charge carrier extraction. The steady-state power output of PSCs based on Spiro-OMeTAD and Pcs dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** are investigated to verify the J at the maximum power point. We noted the Pcs gave stabilized current during the 300 s exposure (Figure 5g). Additionally, we probed PSCs with Spiro-OMeTAD and **ZnPc 3** for operational stability through the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) of the un-encapsulated PSCs under ambient conditions and 1 sun illumination for ~ 95 h, under a relative humidity of 50-60% at 800 mV (Figure 5h). The Spiro-OMeTAD based PSC showed lower stability and retained nearly 32% of its initial J value, while the PSCs based on **ZnPc 3** performed better and displayed a nearly linear response, retaining around >80% of its initial J value after >90 h. We evaluated, the storage stability of the PSCs, and the ZnPc dimers showed improved stability when the PCE was measured periodically (PSCs stored in a dry box) for a month. The normalized PCE of the unencapsulated PSCs with the ZnPc dimers in comparison to Spiro-OMeTAD is displayed (Figure 6a).

Figure 6: (a) Device stability of PSCs with Spiro-OMeTAD and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** under ambient moisture conditions, the PSCs were stored in dark conditions, (b) Nyquist plots for the Spiro-OMeTAD and Pc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** measured with an applied voltage of 950 mV under dark conditions.

Noticeably, both **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3** showed higher stability and retained the initial PCE after >300 h. **ZnPc 2** also showed comparable performance as **ZnPc 1** and **ZnPc 3**, remaining almost 80% of the initial PCE. On the contrary, the Spiro-OMeTAD based PSC showed a decrease in its initial PCE to about 70% and degrades rapidly compared to the ZnPc dimers (visual examination). This suggests the surface properties induce by the ZnPc dimers, favorably prolong the PSCs lifetime, and is also evidenced by the higher contact angle values, which act as an effective shielding of the perovskite layer towards moisture.

We made Mott-Schottky analysis of the PSCs based on Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** (Figure S9). The extracted built-in-potential (V_{bi}) for Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc dimers **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** are 1031 mV, 833 mV, 1014 mV, and 914 mV respectively,² following the V_{oc} trend. We noted increased recombination resistance for **ZnPc 3** based PSC as compared to the **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and Spiro-OMeTAD by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement³⁷ made under dark conditions (Figure 6b). The equivalent circuit used is depicted in Figure S10. The values for R_{recom} for Spiro-OMeTAD, **ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3** based PSCs were calculated to be 1306 Ω , 981.1 Ω , 634.2 Ω and 1679 Ω respectively. The EIS studies suggest the improved interfacial charge extraction, maximum obtained for **ZnPc 3** that subsequently impacts the performance of the PSCs resulting in lower charge recombination at the perovskite/hole selective layer interfaces.

3. Experimental

Materials

Lead Iodide (99.9%) and formamidinium iodide (FAI) was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI) and employed as such. Lead bromide was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Methylammonium bromide (MABr) was purchased from Dyesol. Solvents such as dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethyl formamide (DMF), isopropanol (IPA), ethanol, chlorobenzene were purchased from Acros and used as such.

Phthalocyanine synthesis

All chemicals and solvents were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Merck) and TCI and were used without further purification unless otherwise stated. Zinc 2-iodo-6,16,23-tri-*tert*-butyl-phthalocyaninate was synthesized as described in the literature.³³ Column chromatography was performed with SiO_2 (40–63 μm). ZnPc-t-DPP-t-ZnPc **1**²⁸ and ZnPc-t-t-ZnPc **2**³⁰ were prepared using the methodology already described.

¹H NMR data were recorded with a Bruker AC300 with chemical shifts referenced to residual TMS at 25 °C. Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectra were obtained on a Bruker Microflex LRF20 instrument using dithranol as a matrix. Cyclic voltammetry measurements were performed in 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate

tetrahydrofuran solution as support electrolyte, a graphite working electrode, an Ag/Ag⁺ reference electrode, and a platinum counter electrode using a potentiostat/galvanostat μ Autolab Type III. Ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple (Fc/Fc⁺) was used as an internal standard for all measurements, and 4.8 eV under vacuum was established as the reference level. The HOMO and LUMO levels were estimated using the onset values of reduction and oxidation potentials. UV-vis spectra were measured with a Helios Gamma spectrophotometer and the extinction coefficients were calculated using the Lambert-Beer Law. IR spectra were measured in a KBr matrix with a PerkinElmer Spectrum 3 FT-IR/NIR/FIR spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of ZnPc 1:

Pd₂(dba)₃ (19.6 mg, 0.0214 mmol), CuI (15 mg, 0.0787 mmol) and PPh₃ (45 mg, 0.171 mmol) were mixed in a 25 mL flask under inert atmosphere. Meanwhile, two separated solutions of ethynylZnPc 6 (55 mg, 0.0714 mmol) and Br₂DPP 7 (13.5 mg, 0.02856 mmol) in THF (10 mL) were prepared and degasified in two different flasks. Then the Br₂DPP solution the Et₃N (5 mL) and the ethynylZnPc solution were added to the reaction flask in this order. The reaction was heated to 80 °C and left stirring in darkness for 24 hours. The crude was washed with HCl 1M solution and brine and extracted with DCM. The purification was carried out in a chromatography column with DCM/MeOH 100:1 as eluent obtaining 18 mg (8%) of a dark green powder. ¹H-NMR: (300 MHz, THF-d₈, 25 °C): δ = 9.77-7.89 (m, 28H), 4.60-4.32 (m, 4H), 2.15-1.83 (m, 54H), 1.69-1.59 (m, 16H), 1.19 (s, 12H) ppm.

Synthesis of ZnPc 3:

Route 1: Pd₂(dba)₃ (19.6 mg, 0.0214 mmol), CuI (15 mg, 0.0787 mmol) and PPh₃ (45 mg, 0.171 mmol) were mixed in a 25 mL flask under inert atmosphere. Meanwhile two separated solutions of ethynylZnPc 6 (55 mg, 0.0714 mmol) and 2,7-dibromo-9,9'-spiro[9H-fluorene] (8) (13.5 mg, 0.02856 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL) were prepared and degasified in two different flasks. Then the solution that contained the spiro, the Et₃N (5 mL), and the ZnPc solution were added to the reaction flask in this order. The reaction was heated to 80 °C and left stirring in darkness for 24 hours. The crude product was washed with HCl 1M and brine and extracted with DCM. The purification was carried out in a chromatography column with hexane/THF 1:1 as an eluent obtaining 8 mg (15%) of a green powder.

Route 2: Zinc 2-iodo-6,16,23-tri-*tert*-butyl-phthalocyaninate (4) (35 mg, 0.04 mmol), Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂ (2.8 mg, 4 × 10⁻³ mmol) and CuI (0.4 mg, 2 × 10⁻³ mmol) were dissolved in freshly distilled Et₃N (0.8 mL) and 0.2 mL of dry THF under inert atmosphere. Meanwhile, a separated solution of 2',7'-diethynyl-9,9'-spirobi[9H-fluorene] (9) (29.2 mg, 0.04 mmol) in dry and degasified THF (1 mL) was prepared. This last solution was added to the first one in two equal portions, leaving 2h between each addition. The reaction was stirred at room temperature for 24h. The crude product was washed with HCl 2M and brine and extracted with chloroform. The purification was carried out by chromatography column with hexane/dioxane 2:1 as eluent, obtaining 20 mg (54%) of the dark green powder. ¹H-NMR (300 MHz, THF-d₈, 25 °C): δ = 9.54-9.52 (m, 8H), 9.38-9.37 (m, 8H), 8.34-8.31 (m, 6H), 8.23-8.17 (m, 4H), 8.14-8.12 (m, 2H), 7.92-7.88 (m, 2H), 7.54 (t, J = 12 Hz, 2H), 7.30 (t, J = 12 Hz), 7.19 (s, 2H), 6.96 (d, J = 6 Hz, 2H), 1.88-1.80 (m, 54H) ppm. UV-vis (THF) λ_{\max}/nm (log ϵ): 352 (4.15), 610 (3.66), 671 (4.31), 690 (4.40). HR-MS-MALDI-TOF *m/z*: calculated for C₁₁₇H₉₂N₁₆Zn₂ [M+H]⁺, 1853.6309; found 1853.6291. FT-IR (KBr), ν (cm⁻¹): 3062 (ν C-H Ar), 2954 (ν _A CH₃), 2901 (ν _A CH₂), 2864 (ν _S CH₂), 2201 (ν R-C≡C-R), 1907, 1779, 1734, 1719 (overtone Ar), 1658 (ν C=N), 1612 (Ar ring), 1488, 1448, 1392 (C-N), 1363 (δ C-H), 1330 (C-N), 425 (Zn-N).

Device Fabrication

The fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) coated glass (TEC 7) was used as substrate and was cleaned in sequence before use. Ultrasonication (2% Hellmanex water solution for 30 minutes) followed by rinsing with deionized water, acetone, and then isopropanol (IPA) was used and finally, the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 30 minutes for the removal of organic residue on the surface. TiO₂ compact layer was deposited on this substrate by spray pyrolysis at 500 °C using a precursor solution of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) in anhydrous ethanol (1:19), and the substrates were annealed at 500 °C for further 30 minutes and left to cool down. The mesoporous TiO₂ layer was deposited on top of this through a spin coating process (30 s at 4000 rpm), for this, a TiO₂ paste (Dyesol 30 NR-D) was diluted to 1:8 in ethanol. The TiO₂ coated substrates were annealed first at 125 °C, followed by 500 °C using a programmable ramp in four-step heating, and were finally maintained at 500 °C for 30 min to acquire anatase phase. On attaining room temperature, the substrates were treated under UV-Ozone for 30 minutes and transferred to an argon-filled glove-box for perovskite layer deposition. The precursor solution for preparing the mixed perovskite (MAPbBr₃)_{0.15}(FAPbI₃)_{0.85} was prepared by dissolving FAI (1 M), PbI₂ (1.2 M), MABr (0.2 M), and PbBr₂ (0.2 M) in anhydrous DMF: DMSO 4:1 (v:v). The perovskite solution was spin-coated in a two-step sequence at 1000 and 6000 rpm for 10 and 30 s, respectively. During the second step, 110 μ L of chlorobenzene was dripped as an antisolvent approach on the substrate 5s before the end of the spinning process. The perovskite-coated substrates were annealed at 100 °C for 1 h in a glovebox. On acquiring room temperature, Spiro-OMeTAD (70 mM) and ZnPc dimers (**ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**, 15 mM each) as hole selective layers were deposited by dissolving in chlorobenzene. Spiro-OMeTAD and ZnPc dimers were doped by adding bis-(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide lithium salt (Li-TFSI) and 4-*tert*-Butylpyridine (*t*-BP) in the molar ratio 0.5 and 3.3 respectively. 40 μ L of HTM solutions were spin-coated atop the perovskite layer at 4000 rpm for 30 s, in an argon-filled glove box. The device

fabrication was finished by evaporating an Au layer of 70 nm as a cathode under a low vacuum (10^{-6} torr). All solutions were prepared inside an argon-filled glove box with controlled moisture and oxygen conditions ($O_2 < 10$ ppm, $H_2O < 2$ ppm).

Thin-film Characterization

The thin films were prepared on quartz substrate by spin coating for optical characterization, $(MAPbBr_3)_{0.15}(FAPbI_3)_{0.85}$ with the same concentrations of HTLs employed in PSCs was used. X-ray diffractograms were recorded using the D8 Advance diffractometer from Bruker (Bragg-Brentano geometry, with an X-ray tube Cu $K\alpha$, $\lambda=1.5406$ angstrom). A scan of $5-10^\circ$ was selected with an acquisition time of $1^\circ/\text{min}$. The absorption spectra were measured under a UV-Vis-IR spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 50 UV/Vis Spectrophotometer). Photoluminescence (PL) steady-state measurements were recorded with a spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Instrument LS55).

Device characterization

The device photovoltaics parameters were measured utilizing current density–voltage ($J-V$) curves, registered with a Keithley 2400 source-meter under AM 1.5 G, 100 mW cm^2 illumination from a 450 W AAA solar simulator (ORIEL, 94023 A). NREL certified monocrystalline silicon solar cell was used for calibration. A black metal mask (0.1 cm^2) was used over the active area to reduce the influence of scattered light. The devices were measured at a scan rate: 100 mV s^{-1} , pre-sweep delay: 10 s). The external quantum efficiency (EQE) measurements were carried out using a 150W Xenon lamp attached to with Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4m monochromator as the light source.

4. Conclusions

The position of the diethynyl π -conjugated linkers on the phthalocyanine rings was tuned to synthesize different ZnPc dimers ((**ZnPc 1**, **ZnPc 2**, and **ZnPc 3**). Amendment of the phthalocyanine dimers with the triple bonds and the π -linkers in ZnPc dimers leads to co-planarity in the molecular structure of the core, resulting in competing enhancements of charge extraction and carrier mobility at the perovskite/phthalocyanine interface. Suggested by the investigation of the impact of the substituents' groups in the ZnPc dimers on the hole transport capability and microstructure in thin films. The fabricated perovskite solar cells with the dimer **ZnPc 3** showed a PCE of 18.32%, which surpasses that of the Spiro-OMeTAD (17.42%). The reported performance supersedes previous reports for both ZnPc-based and phthalocyanine-dimers-based hole selective layers, in PSCs. Notably, a very thin layer is used which in turn will consume low materials and reduce the cost. Using admittance spectroscopy, we quantified the performance of the dimers and noted reduced non-radiative recombination at the interface and improved charge transfer kinetics. The ZnPc dimers are shown to be hydrophobic and protect the perovskite layer, thereby will contribute to enhancing the PSC stability.

Author's contribution

D.M., M.J. A., M.C., and L.F. carried out the synthesis and characterization of all the compounds. M.P. performed the experiments, fabricated the devices, analysed the data. M.P., D.M. prepared the initial draft. P.H and S.K. performed the electrical measurements, and S.K. performed the electro-optical measurements and data analysis. S.A. and A.S.S. supervised, drafted, and directed the research. All authors contributed to the draft and prepared the final version.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgments

This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360] and from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (PID2020-117855RB-I00).

References

1. L. Chouhan, S. Ghimire, C. Subrahmanyam, T. Miyasaka and V. Biju, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2020, **49**, 2869-2885.
2. M. Pegu, S. Kazim, T. Buffeteau, D. M. Bassani and S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2021, **13**, 48219-48227.
3. T. Baikie, Y. Fang, J. M. Kadro, M. Schreyer, F. Wei, S. G. Mhaisalkar, M. Graetzel and T. J. White, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2013, **1**, 5628-5641.
4. N.R.E.L, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Research Cell Efficiency Record, <https://www.nrel.gov/pv/cell-efficiency.html>, 2022.
5. J. Jeong, M. Kim, J. Seo, H. Lu, P. Ahlawat, A. Mishra, Y. Yang, M. A. Hope, F. T. Eickemeyer and M. Kim, *Nature*, 2021, **592**, 381-385.
6. R. Wang, M. Mujahid, Y. Duan, Z. K. Wang, J. Xue and Y. Yang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, 2019, **29**, 1808843.
7. K. Rakstys, A. Abate, M. I. Dar, P. Gao, V. Jankauskas, G. Jacopin, E. Kamarauskas, S. Kazim, S. Ahmad, M. Grätzel, M. K. Nazeeruddin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2015, **137**, 16172–16178.
8. H. D. Pham, L. Gil-Escrig, K. Feron, S. Manzhos, S. Albrecht, H. J. Bolink and P. Sonar, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2019, **7**, 12507-12517.

9. H. D. Pham, S. M. Jain, M. Li, Z. K. Wang, S. Manzhos, K. Feron, S. Pitchaimuthu, Z. Liu, N. Motta, J. R. Durrant and P. Sonar, *Adv. Electron. Mater.*, 2020, **6**, 1900884.
10. L. Calió, S. Kazim, M. Grätzel and S. Ahmad, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2016, **55**, 14522-14545.
11. M. Pegu, S. Kazim, P. Huang, L. Lezama and S. Ahmad, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2021, **9**, 7074-7082.
12. K. T. Cho, K. Rakstys, M. Cavazzini, S. Orlandi, G. Pozzi and M. K. Nazeeruddin, *Nano Energy*, 2016, **30**, 853-857.
13. P. Huang, A. Hernández, S. Kazim, J. Follana-Berná, J. Ortiz, L. Lezama, Á. Sastre-Santos and S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, 2021, **4**, 10124-10135.
14. W. Zhou, Z. Wen and P. Gao, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 2018, **8**, 1702512.
15. H. D. Pham, S. M. Jain, M. Li, S. Manzhos, K. Feron, S. Pitchaimuthu, Z. Liu, N. Motta, H. Wang, J. R. Durrant and P. Sonar, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2019, **7**, 5315-5323.
16. S. Kong, X. Wang, L. Bai, Y. Song and F. Meng, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2019, **288**, 111012.
17. M. Urbani, G. de la Torre, M. K. Nazeeruddin and T. Torres, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2019, **48**, 2738-2766.
18. K. Kadish, R. Guilard and K. M. Smith, *The porphyrin handbook: phthalocyanines: spectroscopic and electrochemical characterization*, Academic Press, 2012.
19. L. Calió, J. Follana-Berná, S. Kazim, M. Madsen, H.-G. Rubahn, Á. Sastre-Santos and S. Ahmad, *Sustain. Energy Fuels.*, 2017, **1**, 2071-2077.
20. X. Tang, Q. Liu, C. Wei, X. Lv, Z. Jin, Y. Chen and J. Jiang, *J. Rare Earths.*, 2021, **39**, 113-120.
21. L. Martín-Gomis, F. Fernández-Lázaro and Á. Sastre-Santos, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2014, **2**, 15672-15682.
22. H.-H. Chou, Y.-H. Chiang, M.-H. Li, P.-S. Shen, H.-J. Wei, C.-L. Mai, P. Chen and C.-Y. Yeh, *ACS Energy Lett.*, 2016, **1**, 956-962.
23. S. Kazim, F. J. Ramos, P. Gao, M. K. Nazeeruddin, M. Grätzel and S. Ahmad, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2015, **8**, 1816-1823.
24. Z. Yu, L. Wang, X. Mu, C. C. Chen, Y. Wu, J. Cao and Y. Tang, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2021, **133**, 6364-6369.
25. K. T. Cho, O. Trukhina, C. Roldán-Carmona, M. Ince, P. Gratia, G. Grancini, P. Gao, T. Marszalek, W. Pisula and P. Y. Reddy, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 2017, **7**, 1601733.
26. P. Huang, A. Hernández, S. Kazim, J. Follana-Berná, J. Ortiz, L. Lezama, A. n. Sastre-Santos and S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.*, 2021, **4**, 10124-10135.
27. Y. Matsuo, K. Ogumi, I. Jeon, H. Wang and T. Nakagawa, *RSC Adv.*, 2020, **10**, 32678-32689.
28. Q. Hu, E. Rezaee, L. Dong, Q. Dong, H. Shan, Q. Chen, M. Li, S. Cai, L. Wang and Z.-X. Xu, *Sol. RRL*, 2019, **3**, 1900182.
29. C. L. Mai, Y. L. Huang, G. H. Lee, S. M. Peng and C. Y. Yeh, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2008, **14**, 5120-5124.
30. K. Susumu, P. R. Frail, P. J. Angiolillo and M. J. Therien, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 8380-8381.
31. Y.-H. Chiang, H.-H. Chou, W.-T. Cheng, Y.-R. Li, C.-Y. Yeh and P. Chen, *ACS Energy Lett.*, 2018, **3**, 1620-1626.
32. D. Molina, M. A. Ruiz-Preciado, B. Carlsen, F. T. Eickemeyer, B. Yang, N. Flores-Díaz, M. J. Álvaro-Martins, K. Nonomura, A. Hagfeldt and Á. Sastre-Santos, *ChemPhotoChem*, 2020, **4**, 307-314.
33. D. Molina, M. E. El-Khouly, M. El-Kemary, S. Fukuzumi, F. Fernández-Lázaro and Á. Sastre-Santos, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2016, **22**, 17800-17807.
34. L. A. Illicachi, J. Urieta-Mora, C. Momblona, A. Molina-Ontoria, J. Calbo, J. Aragón, B. Insuasty, A. Ortiz, E. Ortí and N. Martín, *ChemPlusChem*, 2021, **86**, 1006-1013.
35. H. Yoshiyama, N. Shibata, T. Sato, S. Nakamura and T. Toru, *ChemComm.*, 2008, 1977-1979.
36. H. Ali and J. E. van Lier, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2014, **55**, 4163-4167.
37. J. Bisquert, L. Bertoluzzi, I. Mora-Sero and G. Garcia-Belmonte, *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 2014, **118**, 18983-18991.